

Perception of Women on Utilising Government Welfare Schemes In rural areas of Manipur

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Abstract :

In India, where women make up about half of the population, they are guaranteed equal rights under the constitution and are given priority in national development initiatives. A plethora of schemes and programmes have been announced. The utilisation of various schemes varies based on the perception and access which are determined socio economic factors. Hence, the researcher, after careful deliberation has opted to analyze the welfare programmes pertaining to Government Welfare Schemes particularly in the rural sector. The researcher has taken Imphal West District, where the women population is more in rural areas. And 340 respondents were taken for this study using Multi Stage Random Sampling Method. Descriptive Research Design was used for this study. Interview schedule was developed and used as a tool for data collection. The study shows that as the institutional support to the welfare programmes are not oriented in the proper direction and suffer from bias and prejudices, the programmes so launched do not provide the desired benefit to these people in the State, particularly those residing in the rural areas.

Keywords : Perception, Utilisation, Women Welfare, Government Programmes, Rural Areas

Introduction :

A welfare state is one that has effective government operations, prompt redress for citizens, and a system completely free of bribery, corruption, inefficiency, laziness, and the aggravating complexity of bureaucracy, among other negative traits. These are only a few examples of what a welfare state now entails. The citizens of such a State anticipate, among other things, social welfare laws, appropriate medical care,

especially for the elderly, the crippled, and the weak, or, to put it another way, the undeniably weaker segments of society.

Women Welfare:

In India, where women make up about half of the population, they are guaranteed equal rights under the constitution and are given priority in national development initiatives. Numerous plans and initiatives have been constantly published, and on the surface, everything appears to be in place to achieve the goal of the advancement and development of women. But the alarming fact is that since India's independence, the position of women has worsened and declined. In an oppressive patriarchal culture like that of India, women are still submissive to males and have wretched lives in comparison to their male counterparts since they are considered the "Second Sex". In terms of their education, health, and income, rural women also paint a more miserable image than their urban counterparts. Due to the extreme poverty that is widespread in rural regions, rural women in India are subjected to two forms of oppression at once: gender-based marginalisation and their awful living conditions. In India, there is a significant divide between the urban and rural economies, with the latter trailing behind the former significantly in terms of people's lifestyles and socioeconomic levels.

Indian women have a rich history and tradition behind them, which is admirable. It is true, however, that they have suffered greatly under several forms of repression, and all of these must end before they may participate fully in the life of the country.

The national and state governments recognise the progress of women and provide various programmes based on their changing needs and trends. The degree to which people are aware of and have access to such programmes varies depending on their age, marital status, level of education, employment, income, etc. Therefore, this paper analyses awareness and utilisation of Government welfare schemes of women in rural areas of Manipur.

Review of Literature

Bandiera, et.al. (2014) studied that Central and State Governments have introduced various novel schemes for the empowerment of women. Yet minority women are utilizing only selected schemes promoted by the Government due to lack of awareness.

Beaman, et al. (2009) opined that Women entrepreneurs are aware of Mudra Yojana Scheme and Industrial Finance corporation's interest subsidy schemes but as far as the beneficiaries are considered only few are benefited.

Cilliers, (2016) found out Prioritized women empowerment schemes in India such as National policy for empowerment of women, multi-sectoral nutrition programme, Indira Gandhi matritva sahyog yojana (IGMSY), Ujjwala, national mission for empowerment for women, Poorna Shakti Kendra, Rajiv Gandhi national scheme for the children of working mothers and so on for the holistic growth of women.

Koneru, K. (2017) proved that The major challenges faced by women entrepreneur includes lack of marketing opportunities, lack of financial assistance etc.

Kumar, P. (2014) explained that To bring out economic and social development of women and improving their status in the community the programme for Women Development has been introduced.

Venkata, et al. (2020) study that Participation in activities such as political, social or economic activities can be a factor in enhancing the decision-making power as well as personality development of women.

Statement of problems

People in rural areas should get the advantages of the welfare programmes the government has developed to educate the populace; otherwise, these programmes would just serve as paper exercises with no real impact. Second, rural people are the subject of our study because, unlike their urban counterparts, they are not in a position to profit from welfare programmes because of the considerable cultural differences between them and urban people. Welfare programmes in Imphal West, Manipur, would only be able to serve a limited segment of the population's requirements if people living in rural areas are denied access to their benefits. So, after careful consideration, the researcher decided to examine the women's perception pertaining to Government Welfare Schemes particularly in the rural sector.

Objectives

- a) To study the socio economic characteristic of women in study area.
- b) To assess the perception regarding various Government welfare programmes among women.

The following hypotheses are framed based on the above objectives.

- i) There will be no significant difference between awareness and utilization of women welfare programs based on socio-economic variables.
- ii) There will be no association between awareness and utilization of women welfare programs.

Data and Methodology

So for the purpose of the study, the researcher has taken Imphal West District, where the women population is more in rural areas. There are four blocks in Imphal West. They are Lamshang, Patsoi, Lamphelpat and Wangoi. And 340 respondents were taken for this study using Multi Stage Random Sampling Method. Descriptive Research Design was used for this study. Interview schedule was developed and used as a tool for data collection. A pilot study with 40 respondents and pre test was conducted with 20 respondents. The statistical techniques were used to analyse the data are Percentage Analysis, Computation of descriptive statistics like Mean and Std deviation of etc., F-test and Pearson's Product Moment coefficient of correlation(r).

Table: 1 Distribution of the respondents based on age group

Age group	No. Of respondents	Percent
20 to 30	40	11.7
30 to 40	80	23.5
40 to 50	90	26.5
50 Above	130	38.3
Total	340	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 1 discussed with respondents based on age group, 11.7 percent of them have 20 to 30 years of age group, 23.5 percent of them are 30 to 40 years, 26.5 percent of the respondents are 40 to 50 years and 38.3 percent of them have above 50 years of age group.

Table: 2 Distribution of the respondents based on marital status

Marital status	No. Of respondents	Percent
Married	190	55.9
Unmarried	60	17.6
Divorce	10	2.9
Widow	80	23.5
Total	340	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 2 shows the distribution of the respondents based on marital status. It is described from the table that 55.9% of them are married, 17.6% of the respondents are unmarried, 2.9% of them have divorce and 23.5% of them are widow.

Table: 3 Distribution of the respondents based on educational qualification

Educational qualification	No. Of respondents	Percent
10 th	120	35.3
12 th	110	32.4
UG	60	17.6
PG	20	5.9
Others	30	8.8
Total	340	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table discusses the respondents based on educational qualification. It is found that 35.3% of the respondents are 10th, 32.4% of them are 12th, 17.6% of them are UG level, 5.9% of them are PG level and finally 8.8% of them are others qualification level.

Table: 4 Distribution of the respondents based on occupation

Occupation	No. Of respondents	Percent
Govt.	30	8.8
Semi Govt.	20	5.9
Private	40	11.7
Business	50	14.7
Farmers	200	58.8
Total	340	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 4 reveals the distribution of the respondent's based on occupation. 8.8% of them have Government, 5.9% of the respondents are semi Govt., 11.7% of them are private, 14.7% of the respondents are business and the remaining 58.8% of them have farmers.

Table: 5 Distribution of the respondents based on family income

Family income	No. Of respondents	Percent
Less than 10000	40	11.7
10000 to 20000	100	29.4
20000 to 30000	90	26.5
30000 to Above	110	32.4
Total	340	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 5 shows the respondents based on family income. 11.7% of them have less than 10000, 29.4% of them have 10000 to 20000, 26.5% of the respondents are 20000 to 30000 and finally 32.4% of them have above 30000.

Level of perception of government welfare programmes on women livelihood

Perception	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Lack of understanding by the officials of the real problems of the women	68 (20.0)	75 (22.1)	99 (29.1)	56 (16.5)	42 (12.4)
Callousness and lack of commitment of the officials to the programmes	50 (14.7)	63 (18.5)	111 (32.6)	76 (22.4)	40 (11.7)
Lack of intermediaries and opinion leaders	87 (25.6)	72 (21.2)	89 (26.2)	38 (11.2)	54 (15.8)
Lack of strong Organisation for creating protest	84 (24.7)	43 (12.6)	148 (43.5)	28 (8.2)	37 (10.8)
Lack of community support	30 (8.8)	95 (27.9)	144 (42.4)	46 (13.5)	25 (7.4)
Lack of political will	61 (17.9)	84 (24.7)	112 (32.9)	55 (16.2)	28 (8.2)
Programmes are implemented keeping political interest in mind	52 (15.3)	66 (19.4)	146 (42.9)	44 (12.9)	32 (9.4)
Lack of adequate fund	43 (12.6)	80 (23.5)	174 (51.2)	19 (5.6)	24 (7.1)
Corruption among the officials	45 (13.3)	77 (22.6)	104 (30.6)	61 (17.9)	53 (15.6)
Lack of awareness among women	120 (35.3)	89 (26.2)	88 (25.8)	16 (4.7)	27 (7.9)

Source: Primary Data

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Rows	35690.0	9	104836.0	15.32690	0.002369	2.152607
Columns	45112.6	4	11278.15	19.82545	0.01608	2.633532
Error	20479.4	36	568.8722			
Total	65592	49				

Table 4.15 exhibit the details perception of government welfare programmes on women livelihood. Out of 340 respondents. It could be seen from the above discussion that most of the respondents, 51.2% of them have neutral of lack of adequate fund and it is followed by 43.5% of them have Lack of strong Organisation for creating protest for neutral.

It is inferred from the ANOVA table that the calculated P-value is significant. $P < 0.01$ level. So the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Thus, it is concluded that there is a significant difference in perception of government welfare programmes on women livelihood.

Table:4.52

Respondent's level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of age group

Age group	N	Mean	S.D	F-value	p-value
20 to 30	40	15.77	2.88	19.37	0.001 S
30 to 40	80	16.16	3.01		
40 to 50	90	15.62	3.97		
50 above	130	18.29	2.53		
Total	340	16.49	3.17		

Source: Primary Data

The table 4.52 proved that the facts of mean, S.D and F-value for respondents level perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of age group. But it is result discuss from the obtain F-value there is a significant disparity in perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of age group. Since the calculated F-value (19.37) which is significant at 0.001 level. Consequently the stated null hypothesis is rejected and alternated hypothesis is accepted. It is noted that respondents significantly differ in their level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of age group. Considering their obtained mean score (18.29), above 50 years of age group have high level of perception.

Table: 4.55**Respondent's level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of marital status**

Marital status	N	Mean	S.D	F-value	p-value
Married	190	15.46	2.59	55.31	0.001 S
Unmarried	60	17.03	2.82		
Divorce	10	15.90	2.24		
Widow	80	12.83	3.08		
Total	340	15.43	3.13		

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that the specifics of mean, S.D and F-value for respondents level perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of marital status. Although it is result discuss from the obtain F-value there is a significant difference in perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of marital status. Because the calculated F-value (55.31) which is significant at 0.001 level. Consequently the stated null hypothesis is rejected and alternated hypothesis is accepted. It is renowned that respondents significantly differ in their level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of marital status.

Table:4.56**Respondent's level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of educational qualification**

Educational qualification	N	Mean	S.D	F-value	p-value
10 th	120	12.70	1.65	9.38	0.001 S
12 th	110	14.76	3.30		
UG	60	15.44	3.24		
PG	20	15.80	2.23		
Others	30	17.02	1.03		
Total	340	15.26	2.96		

Source: Primary Data

The table 4.56 shows that the specifics of mean, S.D and F-value for respondents level perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of educational qualification. Although it is result discuss from the obtain F-value there is a significant difference in perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of educational qualification. Because the calculated F-value (9.38) which is significant at 0.001 level. Consequently the stated null hypothesis is rejected and alternated hypothesis is accepted. It is renowned that respondents significantly differ in their level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of educational qualification .

Table: 4.57

Respondent's level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of occupation

Occupation	N	Mean	S.D	F-value	p-value
Govt.	30	20.1	0.64	8.60	0.001 S
Semi Govt.	20	16.3	3.97		
Private	40	18.1	1.25		
Business	50	15.7	2.86		
Farmers	200	16.4	3.26		
Total	340	16.49	3.17		

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that the specifics of mean, S.D and F-value for respondents level perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of occupation. Although it is result discuss from the obtain F-value there is a significant difference in perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of occupation. Because the calculated F-value (8.60) which is significant at 0.001 level. Consequently the stated null hypothesis is rejected and alternated hypothesis is accepted. It is renowned that respondents significantly differ in their level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of occupation. Also the government obtained mean score (20.1) have high level of perception and followed by private group mean score (18.1).

Table: 4.58

**Respondent's level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of
Family income**

Family income	N	Mean	S.D	F-value	p-value
Less than 10000	40	14.4	2.51	6.66	0.001 S
10000 to 20000	100	15.2	3.29		
20000 to 30000	90	15.6	3.01		
30000 to Above	110	15.9	2.93		
Total	340	15.2	2.96		

Source: Primary Data

The table 4.58 result exhibits that the information of mean, S.D and F-value for respondents level perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of Family income. While it is result discuss from the attain F-value there is a considerable dissimilarity in perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of Family income. Since the calculated F-value (6.66) which is significant at 0.001 level. Thus the stated null hypothesis is rejected and alternated hypothesis is accepted. It is prominent that respondents significantly differ in their level of perception of government programmes on women livelihood on the basis of Family income. Considering their above 30000 obtained mean score have high perception and followed by 20000 to 30000 income group obtained means score (15.6).

**Correlation analysis among the socio – economic variables and perception of government welfare
programmes on women livelihood**

Socio economic variables	Perception
Age	0.120*
Marital status	-0.069
Educational qualification	0.285**
Occupation	-0.166*
Family income	0.220**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

The table 4.81 result show that the correlation analysis between among the socio-economic variables and perception of government welfare programmes on women livelihood. The perception is positively and significantly related with age, educational qualification and family income. Other variables such as marital status, occupation, are negative relationship.

Finding

- Result shows that respondents based on age group, 11.7 percent of them have 20 to 30 years of age group, 23.5 percent of them are 30 to 40 years, 26.5 percent of the respondents are 40 to 50 years and 38.3 percent of them have above 50 years of age group.
- Outcome displays that based on marital status. It is described from the table that 55.9% of them are married, 17.6% of the respondents are unmarried, 2.9% of them have divorce and 23.5% of them are widow.
- It is noted that based on family income. 11.7% of them have less than 10000, 29.4% of them have 10000 to 20000, 26.5% of the respondents are 20000 to 30000 and finally 32.4% of them have above 30000
- As per the result proved that there is a significant difference in Women's perception on government welfare programmes.
- It is noted that respondents significantly differ in their Women's perception of government programmes on the basis of age group
- Further result shows that respondents significantly differ in their Women's perception of government programmes on the basis of marital status.
- Result discuss that respondents significantly differ in Women's perception of government programmes on the basis of occupation.
- While it is result discuss that respondents significantly differ in their Women's perception of government programmes on the basis of Family income.
- The correlation analysis shows that perception is positively and significantly related with age, educational qualification and family income. Other variables such as marital status and occupation are negative relationship.

Conclusion

A number of welfare schemes have been launched and are continuing in the State to upgrade the position of these people and to ensure that they lead a life of dignity and decency. Many schemes have been sponsored by the Union Government whereas a host of other programmes have been initiated by the State Government. A study has been made of these programmes and it is found that not only the Government of India and the Government of Manipur are spending a huge amount of money for the implementation of these programmes, but also international agencies like the World Bank are rendering considerable financial assistance for such purposes. As far as the quantitative aspect of programmes are concerned, Manipur remains at par, rather is a leading state, as compared to the other states of India

Poverty affects these people due to unequal circumstances. Therefore, these people would still be in want and need, facing a number of problems. On the other hand, we see that though the number of beneficiaries covered under different welfare schemes is on the rise, the coverage potential of such programmes for these people is much less than what is required. Voluntary effort is expected to come up with the necessary resources and services to meet the vast demand. These people are functioning for the purpose of implementation of welfare programmes for with necessary help from voluntary organizations and to sort out the problems concerning these people respectively. All the institutions are working with definite aims and objectives of improving the status of these people

It was ultimately inferred that the officials, policy makers and workers of different institutions set up for these people welfare possess an attitude of viewing these people in stereotype roles of wives and mothers and accordingly they design and deliver services under these misconceptions. The study shows that as the institutional support to the welfare programmes are not oriented in the proper direction and suffer from bias and prejudices, the programmes so launched do not provide the desired benefit to these people in the State, particularly those residing in the rural areas.

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